

Role of Immunohistochemistry in the Diagnosis of Malignant LymphomasChalana¹, Shantha Krishnamurthy²¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pathology, Varun Arjun Medical College and Rohilkhand Hospital, Banthra Shahjahanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India²Professor, Triesta Reference Laboratory, Bangalore Institute of Oncology, A unit of Health Care Global Enterprises Ltd, Hospital, Bangalore, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** The complexities of diagnostic haematopathology are well known, and even in this molecular era, immunophenotypic studies together with routine histopathology remain critical components in the evaluation of lymphoid proliferations. Immunohistochemistry refines diagnoses, impacts therapeutics, and influences prognosis.**Aims:** This study aimed to review the histomorphology of nodal and extranodal malignant lymphomas and correlate histopathologic diagnoses with immunohistochemistry (IHC) results in malignant nodal and extranodal lymphomas.**Methods:** This retrospective cohort study investigated the role of IHC in diagnosing malignant lymphomas at Triesta Reference Laboratory, Health Care Global - Bangalore Institute of Oncology. Ethical approval was obtained, and 100 patients diagnosed between January 2009 to July 2009 were included. These patients visited Health Care Global - Bangalore Institute of Oncology (HCG-BIO) out-patient departments, and cases were referred from HCG branches all over India, hospitals, and laboratories in and around Bangalore for review. Clinical information, histopathological, and IHC slides were systematically collected. Data, including demographics, symptoms, imaging findings, and follow-up information, were analyzed using SPSS 18. IHC utilized a panel of antibodies, and tests for proportions assessed concordance and discordance between diagnostic methods.**Results:** In the study of 100 cases, 82 were nodal lymphomas, among which 11 were of Hodgkin's type and 71 of non-Hodgkin's type (57 B-cell, 12 T-cell, and 2 gray zone lymphomas). Additionally, 18 cases were extranodal, encompassing Diffuse Large B-cell lymphomas (DLBCL), Peripheral T-cell lymphomas (PTCL), Cutaneous T-cell lymphomas (CTCL), Lymphoblastic Lymphomas (LBL), Mucosa-Associated Lymphoid Tissue Lymphomas (MALToma), and Marginal Zone Lymphomas (MZL). The concordance between histopathological diagnosis and IHC results was 75%, demonstrating significant overall agreement ($p < 0.001$).**Conclusion:** Precise diagnosis and classification of lymphomas are imperative for tailored management, particularly in emergency oncologic scenarios. IHC is essential and integral to lymphoma diagnosis.**Keywords:** Histomorphology, Immunohistochemistry, Lymphomas, Concordance, Essential, Integral.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The complexities of diagnostic haematopathology are well known, and even in this molecular era, immunophenotypic studies together with routine histopathology remain critical components in the evaluation of lymphoid proliferations. With the numerous antibodies that can be used on routinely fixed paraffin-embedded tissue sections (FFPE), IHC has become increasingly valuable [1,2].

The clinical and/or morphologic study may not be specific in classifying lymphomas into types and subtypes, and hence immunophenotyping remains a critical component in determining the cell lineage [3,4]. Although in the early 1980s a routine panel

included less than 10 antibodies, the current armamentarium includes more than 50 antibodies. Additionally, there are more than 300 antigens listed in the current Cluster of Differentiation (CD) list, including antigens expressed on non-leucocytes (stromal cells, endothelial cells, etc.) [5,6].

This explosion of antigens and reagents to detect them necessitates the judicious use of carefully selected panels rather than a shotgun approach to diagnosis [7,8]. It then becomes a challenge for the practicing pathologist to know the best approach to the selection and interpretation of antibodies in arriving at a diagnosis [9].

The goals of this study are to provide guidance to the practicing pathologist in the appropriate selection of an antibody panel based on morphology and relevant clinical data and to avoid pitfalls in the interpretation of immunohistochemical data [10,11]. This study provides a comprehensive review of each lymphoma, antibodies used, and technical issues involved in IHC. The reader is referred to several other articles for additional information.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This study employed a retrospective cohort design to investigate the role of IHC in the diagnosis of malignant lymphomas. The study was conducted at Triesta Reference Laboratory (TRL), Health Care Global - Bangalore Institute of Oncology (HCG-BIO), and ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee prior to commencement.

Patient Selection: A total of 100 patients diagnosed with malignant lymphomas between January 2009 and July 2009 were included in the study. The cases encompassed patients visiting the HCG-BIO outpatient departments, as well as those received from HCG branches all over India, hospitals, and laboratories in and around Bangalore for review.

The study was conducted by collecting all cases diagnosed as lymphomas from the files of TRL during the period mentioned above. Clinical information of each patient was obtained by retrieving medical records at HCG-BIO. Patients with inadequate tissue samples for immunohistochemical analysis or a history of previous lymphoma treatment were excluded from the study.

Tissues from all the cases utilized for the study were formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded. The sections were Haematoxylin and Eosin stained. IHC on these sections was performed manually by the polymeric labeled two-step method (Dako REAL EnVision detection system) after heat-induced epitope retrieval using diaminobenzidine (DAB) as chromogen.

The IHC panel was selected based on the histologic appearances. An algorithmic approach towards the selection of IHC markers on the basis of histologic appearance was utilized. Non-lymphoma markers were used in some cases.

The following antibodies were used in the study: CD3, CD5, CD10, CD15, CD23, CD30, CD43, CD45, CD68, CD79a, CD99, CD138, BCL-2, Cyclin-D1, CK (Cytokeratin), Desmin, Ki67, Myeloperoxidase (MPO), Neuron-specific enolase (NSE), Placental Alkaline Phosphatase (PLAP), S-100, Smooth muscle actin (SMA), Vimentin (all ready-to-use antibodies from Biogenex, San Ramon, California), ALK-1 (1:50), BCL-6 (1:10), CD20 (1:400), CD-117 (1:400) (all from Dakocytomation,

Denmark), and CD56 (ready-to-use) from Novocastra, Newcastle Upon Tyne, UK.

The Ki67 proliferation index was calculated using the mean percentage of 500 positive nuclei in 10 HPFs (40X).

A standard proforma was prepared for uniform documentation of each patient's history, clinical and imaging findings, histomorphology, IHC panels used, and coding each parameter.

Statistical Analysis: The data analysis was conducted utilizing SPSS 18 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software for Windows. Descriptive statistics were applied through the generation of frequency distributions for all categorical variables. In order to validate concordance and discordance, various tests for proportions were employed, including Pearson's chi-square, Kendall's coefficient of concordance, and directional measures such as Somer's d.

Ethical Considerations: This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained from patients or their legal representatives, and all patient-related data were anonymized to ensure confidentiality.

Results

In the examination of one hundred biopsy slides, the distribution of non-Hodgkin lymphoma cases (n=89) according to age and sex revealed a predominant occurrence in the fifth and sixth decades of life. Males surpassed females at a ratio of 2:1, with a median age at presentation of 52 years. Gender-wise, the median age for males was 50 years, and for females, it was 54 years. The age range varied from the youngest recorded case at 6 years to the oldest at 87 years.

Among Hodgkin lymphoma cases (n=11), the highest frequency was observed in the second decade of life, with males outnumbering females at a ratio of 1.7:1. The median age at presentation was 33 years, with a median age of 38.5 years for males and 24.2 years for females. The age spectrum for Hodgkin lymphoma cases ranged from 15 years as the youngest recorded to 80 years as the oldest. In our study, the majority of cases were of nodal origin. Lymphadenopathy (localized or generalized) in nodal cases ranged from 3 to 18 months. The maximum number of biopsies was from the cervical region (31%), followed by axillary (18%) and extranodal sites (18%). In two cases, the site of biopsy was not mentioned. Fifty percent of the patients either had no B symptoms or symptoms were not recorded. Four of them presented with other symptoms such as blackouts (due to anemia), pressure symptoms (due to hepatosplenomegaly/ascites), pruritus, and dyspnea. Imaging was done in 80% of the patients, either for

staging or for obtaining guided biopsies in extranodal cases and from lymphadenopathies in inaccessible sites. The majority of the patients were in Stage IA/B at the time of presentation, more so in cases of aggressive lymphomas than in indolent ones. Three cases presented with splenomegaly, of

which one was a case of splenic marginal zone lymphoma. In 72% of the patients, hematological parameters were within normal limits. Twenty-eight patients presented with anemia and/or leucopenia/thrombocytopenia/leukoerythroblastic reaction (Table 1).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the Lymphoma cases

Variables	Frequency
Type of involvement	
Nodal	82
Abdominal	6
Retroperitoneal	10
Inguinal	4
Para aortic	1
Iliac	1
Cervical	31
Axillary	18
Site not mentioned	2
Extra nodal	18
B symptoms	
No symptoms/not known	50
Fever	4
Pain	3
Weakness	5
Weight loss	1
Malaise	2
Combination	31
Others	4
Clinical Staging	
IA	27
IB	14
IIA	3
IIB	4
IIIA	13
IIIB	15
IVA	1
IVB	3
IE A	7
IE B	4
IIEA	1
IIEB	1
IIIE B	4
III ES A	1
III ES B	1
IIIS B	1

In 24 patients, biopsies were done with endoscopic or CT (computerized tomographic scan) guidance in cases where the nodes were in inaccessible sites (retroperitoneal, para-aortic, etc.) and in extranodal cases. In this study, biopsy distribution included Excision Biopsy (27%), Slide for Review (54%), Resection (9%), Incision (1%), Core Biopsy (1%), Tru-Cut (7%), and Others (1%). Notably, 54% of the received material consisted of slides for review from HCG branches across India and in and around Bangalore. Sixty-three cases had totally effaced architecture of the node, and 48 showed

extracapsular extension (perinodal spread). In some cases, the capsule could not be seen because of limited biopsy sampling. Almost all non-Hodgkin lymphoma cases had a monomorphic cell type, except for cases of Peripheral T-cell Lymphoma, Not Otherwise Specified (PTCL NOS), some Marginal Zone Lymphomas (MZLs), Angioimmunoblastic T-cell lymphomas, etc., compared to Hodgkin lymphoma patients who had a polymorphous cell population. A diffuse pattern of involvement of the nodes/extranodal sites was seen in more than half of the cases. In our study, the

majority of cases (99%) showed no associated lesions, while a single case (1%) exhibited granulomas (Tables 2-7).

Table 2: Architectural Patterns Observed in Biopsy Samples

Architecture	Frequency
Totally effaced	63
Partially effaced	16
Not effaced	3
Not applicable	18

Table 3: Cell Composition Distribution in Malignant Lymphoma Cases (Monomorphous)

Cell composition (Monomorphous)	Frequency
Small cell	20
Medium cell	06
Large cell	23
Blastic	01
Anaplastic	03
Plasmacytoid differentiation	08
Combination	18

Table 4: Cell Composition Distribution in Malignant Lymphoma Cases (Polymorphous)

Cell composition (Polymorphous)	Frequency
Hodgkin disease & subtypes	11
Others	10

Table 5: Distribution of Architectural Patterns in Malignant Lymphoma Cases

Patterns	Frequency
Nodular	32
Diffuse	54
Mixed	13
Others	1

Table 6: Distribution of Capsule Integrity in Malignant Lymphoma Cases

Capsule	Frequency
Intact	34
Not intact	48
Not applicable	18

Table 7: Distribution of Associated Lesions in Malignant Lymphoma Cases

Associated lesions	Frequency
No associated lesions	99
Granulomas	1

In 43 patients, bone marrow examination was not conducted, while 57 patients underwent bone marrow aspiration and/or biopsy, among whom 15 showed marrow involvement, indicating Stage IV disease. To summarize, with the exception of a single case initially diagnosed as MC CHL on H&E but confirmed as ALCL, ALK [+], after IHC, all other cases exhibited concordance between the histopathological examination (HPE) diagnosis and the final diagnosis after IHC.

The discordance in the diagnosis of small cell lymphomas mainly pertained to subcategorization. In diagnosing DLBCL, discordance was noted in two cases with medium-sized nuclei, some showing

prominent nucleoli, giving a picture more indicative of blastic lymphoma rather than a large cell lymphoma. In two other cases, neoplastic cells were in cohesion, one showing a peculiar alveolar pattern, thereby suggesting a possibility of undifferentiated carcinoma in the differential. In another case, a polymorphous population with RS-like cells and smudged nuclei was noted, categorized under a broad division of haematolymphoid malignancy on HPE, which turned out to be T/HRBCL after IHC.

Among blastic lymphomas, one was thought to be of reactive nature on HPE due to partial nodal involvement, since LBLs most commonly present as complete nodal involvement. IHC is mandatory in

these cases to confirm the lineage (B/T cell type). All cases diagnosed as PTCL-NOS (nodal & extranodal) were classified under the broad category of haematolymphoid malignancy NOS. Polymorphous populations with RS-like cells were seen on HPE in these cases, bringing a number of differentials into the picture; hence, a precise diagnosis could be made only after IHC.

One case of extranodal lymphoma of the jejunum was classified under a broad heading of intestinal T-cell lymphoma, ALK negative, due to morphological overlap, incomplete clinical and immunohistochemical information, and a lack of molecular study facility in the Triesta laboratory for a precise diagnosis. Gray zone lymphomas (nodal and extranodal) with features intermediate between DLBCL and BL were finally diagnosed with the aid of the proliferation marker Ki67/MIB1. Another case, which had overlapping features of both HL and ALCL, was categorized as a Gray Zone Lymphoma

with features intermediate between CHL and ALCL ALK [—] CD30+ after IHC (Tables 8A-F and Figure 1-3).

In our study, the comparison between histopathologic diagnosis and final diagnosis after immunohistochemistry (IHC) revealed a high level of concordance, with 75% of cases demonstrating agreement. However, 25% of cases exhibited discordance between the initial histopathologic diagnosis and the final diagnosis following IHC (Figure 4). There was significant overall concordance of IHC diagnosis with HPE diagnosis with Pearson's chi-square, $X^2=32.9$, $p=0.03$. Further, Kendall's coefficient of concordance was also significant with $X^2=1.4$, $p<0.001$. Directional measures such as Somer's d was also significant assuming the null hypothesis that the diagnosis by IHC and HPE are no different. Somer's $d=5.83$, $p<0.001$.

Table 8 A: Comparison of HPE diagnosis with final diagnosis after IHC evaluation for nodal lymphomas (Hodgkin Lymphoma: 11 cases)

H & E Diagnoses	Final diagnosis
NLPHL (1)	NLPHL (1)
NS-CHL (6)	NS-CHL (6)
MC-CHL (3)	MC-CHL (3)
LD-CHL (1)	LD-CHL (1)

Table 8 B: Comparison of HPE diagnosis with final diagnosis after IHC evaluation for nodal lymphomas (Small B-cell lymphomas: 23 cases)

H & E Diagnoses	Final diagnosis
Small cell lymphoma not specified (5)	SLL (4), NMZL (1)
SLL (1)	SLL (1)
NMZL (3)	NMZL (2), MCL (1)
FL (12)	FL (12)
MCL (2)	MCL (2)

Table 8 C: Comparison of HPE diagnosis with final diagnosis after IHC evaluation for nodal lymphomas (High grade aggressive B-cell lymphomas: 34 cases)

H & E Diagnoses	Final diagnosis
Blastid (2)	DLBCL (2)
Undifferentiated Ca vs Lymphoma (2)	DLBCL (2)
DLBCL (29)	DLBCL (28)
T/HRBCL (1)	T/HRBCL (1)
Haematolymphoid malignancy	T/HRBCL (1)

Table 8 D: Comparison of HPE diagnosis with final diagnosis after IHC evaluation for nodal lymphomas (T-cell lymphomas: 12 cases)

H & E Diagnoses	Final diagnosis
Reactive vs neoplastic (1)	LBL (1)
LBL (2)	LBL (2)
Haematolymphoid malignancy (4)	LBL (1)
AITL (1)	LBL (2)
ALCL (3)	ALCL ALK (+)-2 ALCL ALK (-)-1
MC-CHL (1)	ALCL ALK (+)-1

Table 8 E: Comparison of HPE diagnosis with final diagnosis after IHC evaluation for nodal lymphomas (Gray zone Lymphomas: 2 cases)

H & E Diagnoses	Final diagnosis
? HL? ALCL (1)	GZ-intermediate between CHL & ALCL, ALK (-) CD30 +
DLBCL (1)	GZ – intermediate between DLBCL & Burkitt's (1)

Table 8 F: Comparison of HPE diagnosis with final diagnosis after IHC evaluation for Extranodal Lymphomas: 18 cases

H & E Diagnoses	Final diagnosis
Reactive (medial canthus) – (1)	MALT lymphoma [1]
Undifferentiated malignant tumour [jejunum, mandible]— [2]	Intestinal-lymphoma, ALK (-) [1] DLBCL [1]
Haematolymphoid malignancy rt. humerus, tonsil, breast— [3]	DLBCL [1] PTCL NOS [1] PTCL NOS [1]
LBL [thymus]— [1]	T-LBL [1]
MAL lymphomas [gastric {2}, orbital {1}]— [3]	DLBCL [1] MALT lymphomas [2]
DLBCL {tonsil [2], liver [1], TAH+BSO [1], colon [1], caecum [1]}	DLBCL [5] GZ-DLBCL&BL [1]
Cutaneous/blastic lymphoma/granulocytic sarcoma [1]	CTCL: PTCL NOS [1]
Spleen [SMZL]— [1]	SMZL [1]

[NLPHL (Nodular Lymphocyte-Predominant Hodgkin Lymphoma), NS-CHL (Nodular Sclerosis Classical Hodgkin Lymphoma), MC-CHL (Mixed Cellularity Classical Hodgkin Lymphoma), LD-CHL (Lymphocyte-Depleted Classical Hodgkin Lymphoma), SLL (Small Lymphocytic Lymphoma), NMZL (Nodal Marginal Zone Lymphoma), MCL (Mantle Cell Lymphoma), FL (Follicular Lymphoma), DLBCL (Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma), T/HRBCL(T-Cell/Histiocyte-Rich Large B-Cell Lymphoma), LBL (Lymphoblastic Lymphoma), AITL (Angioimmunoblastic T-Cell Lymphoma), ALCL (Anaplastic Large Cell Lymphoma), GZ (Gray

Zone), MALT (Mucosa-Associated Lymphoid Tissue), PTCL NOS (Peripheral T-Cell Lymphoma, Not Otherwise Specified), SMZL (Splenic Marginal Zone Lymphoma), CTCL (Cutaneous T-Cell Lymphoma), HL (Hodgkin Lymphoma), ALK (Anaplastic Lymphoma Kinase), CD30 (Cluster of Differentiation 30), Ca (Carcinoma), IHC (Immunohistochemistry), GZL (Gray Zone Lymphoma), Burkitt's (Burkitt's Lymphoma), jejunum (Jejunum - part of the small intestine), RT (Right), TAH+BSO (Total Abdominal Hysterectomy with Bilateral Salpingo-Oophorectomy), and SMZL (Splenic Marginal Zone Lymphoma).]

Figure 1: [A] Photomicrograph of lymph node involved by T-lymphoblastic lymphoma. [H&E. 40x] There is monotonous infiltrate of medium-sized cells with nuclei, fine chromatin, indistinct nucleoli with brisk mitotic activity. [B] The neoplastic cells show positive [nuclear] immunostaining for TdT [10x]

Figure 2: Photomicrograph of stomach involved by MALT lymphoma (H&E, 4%40x) respectively. [A] Typical lymphoepithelial lesions noted. [B] Mixture of cell types include centrocyte-like cells, monocytoid cells and plasma cells

Figure 3: Photomicrographs of lymph nodes involved by lymphomas depicting Ki67 [nuclear] immunostaining [40x]. A guide to differentiate between low- and high-grade lymphomas, the cut off being more than 40%. [A1 & A2] Follicular lymphoma with diffuse & nodular areas respectively, Ki67; 15-20% [B] Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, Ki67, 75-80% [C] Gray zone lymphoma – intermediate between DLBCL and Burkitt’s, ki67;>95%

Figure 4. Concordance and discordance of histopathologic diagnosis with final diagnosis after IHC

As evident from the above figure concordance of HPE with final diagnosis after IHC was maximum in Follicular Lymphoma, followed by HL and DLBCL. Maximum discordance was seen in PTCL-NOS

Discussion

The present study delves into the role of immunohistochemistry (IHC) in the diagnosis of malignant lymphomas, encompassing a comprehensive analysis of one hundred cases. The study systematically focuses on the morphologic assessment of lymphoid proliferations with further use of IHC markers and correlation with clinical information, imaging studies, and laboratory investigations in arriving at a final diagnosis for the judicious management of lymphoma patients.

Some of the limitations of this study have already been alluded to. However, it is also prudent to mention that there was no control/discretion over the selection of either the site of biopsy or the nature of the biopsy. In some cases, the entire IHC panel was performed on core biopsies, which are not ideal tissues for the diagnosis of lymphoma, posing histologic dilemmas to the pathologist [12].

Being a retrospective study, it was noted that there was no uniformity with regard to the selection of the IHC panel since the reports were generated by more than one pathologist. Thus, in some cases, there was the use of either less or more than what was necessary as dictated by H&E appearances. As far as the IHC panel is concerned, some antibodies were not optimally reactive, e.g., CD79a and CD15. Because of the limitations of this study, the role of IHC in separating reactive from neoplastic states could not be fully evaluated. In fact, IHC plays a very important role in this area, with the percentage of neoplastic lymphoid proliferations in cases of all lymphadenopathies being as low as 1.1%, according to other studies [1,13,14]. The other important area is differentiating metastatic undifferentiated carcinoma from lymphoma, which also could not be fully evaluated for the reasons stated.

There were no cases of HIV/AIDS-related and post-transplant lymphoproliferative disorders in this study. However, in larger series, their percentage is 3% and 1-10% of all lymphomas, respectively [1].

As presented in the results in this series of one hundred cases, non-Hodgkin lymphoma formed the bulk. The age at presentation of NHL was a decade earlier than in some other series [2,13,15]. However, the male-to-female ratio appears to be similar [1,15,16]. The commonest site of biopsy was the cervical lymph node, and most lacked B symptoms or they were not recorded, similar to other studies [17,18].

The higher-grade lymphomas were more localized compared to low grade lymphomas, which presented

with advanced clinical stage and marrow involvement [2,13,15]. A good quality paraffin-embedded hematoxylin and eosin-stained section and IHC remains the cornerstone of the diagnosis of a hematolymphoid malignancy [1].

As has been pointed out under the approach to diagnosis, small cell lymphomas are a heterogeneous category, which in a proper clinical context can lead to a correct diagnosis but may be problematic in some cases [10,11,17,18]. In this study, difficulties were encountered in the categories of MZL and MCL and in some cases of SLL where a precise diagnosis could be given only after IHC [5,19]. The diagnosis of FL could be made confidently on H&E-stained sections. BCL-2, an anti-apoptotic marker, helped to confirm the same [20].

In the present study, FL constituted the largest number of small cell lymphomas followed by MZL, including MALTomas and SLL, in accordance with another larger study in India done by Naresh et al., [3]. High grade lymphomas also exhibit diversities, which include small cell, medium, large cell, and mixed categories, along with the criteria for diagnosis and pitfalls in the differential. The grade is usually assigned using the MIB-1/Ki-67 marker since mitoses are not always easy to identify on H&E-stained sections. The same was utilized in the study to differentiate high grade from low grade lymphomas, the cutoff being more than 40% [1,4,8].

Problems arise in small to medium-sized cell high grade lymphomas like LBL when the node is partially involved, as happened in a single case. Generally, LBL shows diffuse involvement of lymph nodes [1,15]. There were no cases of BL in this series. However, larger series have reported around 0.56-0.6% of all lymphomas in the study as Burkitt's [21].

High grade large cell lymphomas are easy to diagnose on H&E sections. However, undifferentiated metastatic carcinomas may mimic lymphomas, making the diagnosis much more crucial in cases of occult primary, in which cases IHC is of prime importance [19]. DLBCL was the most common diagnosis among the large cell lymphomas, which is similar to other series and all were of the centroblastic type. The majority of the cases in the present study were of NHL-DLBCL subtype followed by FL. The same is extrapolated by other larger series [3].

Further subtyping of DLBCL into germinal center or non-germinal center types based on a panel of five markers, namely BCL-6, CD10, MUM1/IRF4, GCET1, and FOX P1 (new algorithm) for prognostic purposes is recommended. However, this study being retrospective, the information regarding the same was not available. BCL-2, done on a few cases, helped us to assess the prognosis to a limited

extent, with BCL-2 positive lymphomas being said to have a poor prognosis [14,22].

There was one case of transformed lymphoma in this study: lymphoplasmacytic lymphoma transformed to DLBCL. Few studies indicate that around 10-70% of all low-grade lymphomas transform to high grade, with the most common being follicular lymphoma of an aggressive histologic type [6,15]. Studies focusing on the transformation of only LPL to high-grade lymphoma (DLBCL) show 5% and 13% of cases said to have undergone transformation in two different studies [23]. Older age (>60-70), male sex, poor performance status, organomegaly, cytopenias, heavy tumor burden, hypoalbuminemia, cryoglobulinemia, polymorphous histology, and complex cytogenetic abnormalities including deletion of 6q16 and 6q21 are factors that influence transformation [23]. In this study, the LPL patient was 70 years old with bicytopenia.

Regarding T-cell lymphomas, PTCL NOS accounted for the majority among all the T-cell types, followed by LBL and ALCL, with only a single case of AITL wherein clinical correlation plays a crucial role. This is in contradiction to the largest study conducted in India by Naresh et al. and his colleagues wherein LBL formed the majority of all T-cell lymphomas, followed by ALCL, with PTCL NOS accounting for the least [3].

Peripheral T-cell lymphomas are difficult to diagnose on routine H&E sections because these are usually polymorphous with RS-like cells. However, some clues to the diagnosis include an increase in high endothelial venules, irregular nuclei, and cytoplasmic clearing. Even with IHC, the confirmation is not always easy [1,24]. Correlation with the clinical picture, imaging, etc., is necessary. The lack of molecular studies in most institutes is a drawback [1,24]. In our study, most cases of PTCL were simply reported as hematomalymphoid malignancy, NOS. The final diagnosis of PTCL was arrived at after taking into account some of the features mentioned above along with immunohistochemical results. ALCL, which formed 4% of the cases, was diagnosed based on morphology, the presence of characteristic hallmark cells, and CD30 positivity shown by the neoplastic cells on IHC. ALK-1 expression was seen in 3% of them, in accordance with other studies which state that 60-85% of all ALCLs are ALK-1 positive. ALK-1 negative cases are said to have a poor prognosis [7,23]. There were no cases of other types of T-cell lymphomas in this study, such as variants of PTCL-NOS (Lennert lymphoma, follicular or T-zone variants, subcutaneous panniculitis-like T-cell lymphoma, extranodal NK/T-cell lymphoma, nasal type, etc.) [1].

HL formed 11% of the cases in the present study, the proportion as compared to NHL, age/sex

distribution being similar to other reported series [1,15,16]. The cervical lymph node was the most common biopsy site. In comparison to NHL, the HL cases were more localized (stage I and II). However, in contrast to NHL, all the patients had B symptoms at presentation [1,15,16].

IHC has enabled a confident diagnosis of this disease. The only problem encountered in the study was probably more technical, as there was a lack of consistency with the CD15 marker, but the cellular composition was diagnostic enough. Studies have shown that CD15 is positive in 75-85% of all CHLs [1]. Moreover, other studies have stated that the lack of CD15 expression is associated with advanced age, male predominance, higher stage, more so in MC CHL than NS CHL. However, in contradiction to this finding, more than 50% of our cases belonged to NS CHL subtype, with presentation at a younger age, stage I-II with almost equal sex incidence, and was associated with the lack of CD15 expression [7,14].

One case of syncytial variant of NS CHL was seen in the study, which is said to have a poor prognosis compared to the non-syncytial variant [7]. Diagnostic difficulties may be encountered in previously treated cases of lymphomas with recurrence, as happened in three cases, two NHLs and one HL in this study, the same is supported by other studies [3,7].

With regard to extranodal lymphomas, the commonest site of involvement was the gastrointestinal tract [3], followed by the tonsil [14] and orbit [2], in contradiction to another larger study in India wherein the tonsil was the commonest site, unlike western literature quoting the gastrointestinal tract as the most common site of primary extranodal NHL [2,14].

DLBCL was the most common type, as supported by other studies done in India [3]. It is tempting to suggest that this finding reflects a high-grade transformation of a low-grade lymphoma, either marginal or mantle cell type, more commonly said to occur at these sites but frequently overlooked by the surgical pathologists, at the time of initial presentation. Since in lymphomatous infiltrates composed of small cells, the obvious malignant features seen in large cell extranodal lymphomas are lacking, making the differential diagnosis more challenging; with many pathologists ending up reporting these as pseudolymphomas [2]. Hence, studies have suggested that correlation with clinical parameters and integration of morphologic findings with ancillary techniques are often indispensable in arriving at a correct diagnosis [2].

Some unusual sites of extranodal lymphomas noted in this study were PTCL NOS of the breast [1] and bone [1]. Single cases of Splenic MZL, CTCL were

also noted in the series, similar to that accounted for by other larger series [2,14,25].

Three cases were classified as gray zone lymphomas in this study: two with features intermediate between Burkitt and DLBCL and one intermediate between CHL and ALK-negative ALCL. This is a major problem area for both pathologists and hematologists as it has direct implications on management strategies.

Limitations

Complete clinical information was not available in all cases, regarding the site of biopsy, staging, etc. There was a selection bias, as all cases included in the study had a final diagnosis of lymphoma; thus, many cases were automatically excluded from the study. Examples include reactive versus neoplastic and carcinoma versus lymphoma cases, where IHC is of prime importance. Additional IHC could not be carried out in required cases for various reasons such as: the study being retrospective, non-availability of paraffin block, and non-availability of antibodies. A few examples include DLBCL that could not be subtyped into GCB and non-GCB categories. Similarly, subset phenotyping of T-cell lymphomas based on CD4 and CD8 expression could not be carried out.

Conclusion

Diagnosis and further classification of lymphomas into distinct disease entities are crucial, as management protocols vary for different types, with some, like lymphoblastic lymphoma and Burkitt lymphoma, being oncologic emergencies. Lymphoma diagnosis involves a multiparameter approach, most importantly meticulous H&E examination (morphology), followed by IHC, cytogenetics, and molecular genetics.

IHC is no longer an ancillary technique for lymphoma diagnosis; it is essential and integral, especially in low-grade NHL, in distinguishing reactive from neoplastic lymphoid proliferation, and in typing NHL. Morphology serves as the basis for ordering any diagnostic algorithms used for applying IHC. To devise diagnostic panels for different types of lymphomas, one must rely on their own expertise and the best available external evidence.

No antigen is entirely lineage-specific or lymphoma-specific; therefore, immunostaining must be interpreted in the context of a panel and morphology to avoid errors in assigning cell lineage or abnormal phenotype. Understanding the antigen's expression in normal, reactive, and neoplastic states, and correlating with clinical and imaging studies, is crucial.

Each lymphoid neoplasm has a characteristic immunophenotype, but a potential pitfall is the small

number of otherwise typical cases expressing phenotype markers of other neoplasms or lacking their characteristic markers.

IHC not only aids in diagnosis but also in assessing prognosis, such as MIB1 labeling index in FL and DLBCL, CD57 in T-LBL, BCL-2 in DLBCL, and cyclin D1 in plasma cell dyscrasias. Clonality assessment by immunophenotyping is possible only in some B-cell lesions, while T-cell clonality assessment requires gene rearrangement studies. New markers are continuously emerging for lymphoid and accessory cells, active in paraffin sections, improving the standard and reproducibility of lymphoma diagnosis. However, interpreting results with existing agents can be challenging, and reagents are expensive, with methods demanding in time and expertise.

Further studies will be necessary to establish the true value of paraffin section IHC in diagnostic lymphoma pathology.

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